

Electrospray ionization (ESI) and Nano-spray ionization

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Didactic 4: electrospray ionization (ESI)

1. Experimental setup
2. The electrospray process
 1. Droplet formation
 2. Droplet fission
 3. Ion production from the droplets
 - a. Ion evaporation mechanism (IEM)
 - b. Charged residue mechanism (CRM)
 - c. Chain ejection mechanism (CEM)
 - d. Competition between mechanisms, hybrid mechanism
3. Typical electrospray ionization mass spectra
4. Relative response of analytes in electrospray
5. Nano-electrospray ionization and the effect of initial droplet size

Electrospray in other research fields

Electrospray deposition of nanoparticles

[Zhu and Chiarot, *J. Mater. Sci.* \(2019\) 54, 6122](#)

Electrospinning of fibers

[Isaac et al., *Fibers* \(2021\) 9, 4](#)

Electrospray ionization (ESI) for mass spectrometry

J. B. Fenn, Nobel prize 2002

« Electrospray wings for Molecular Elephants »

[Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. \(2003\) 42, 3871](#)

Electrospray experimental setup

Electrospray experimental setup

Early days: on-axis

Nowadays: off-axis

Electrospray Process

Ion production => electric current, maintained by oxydation/reduction

Electrospray Process

1) Taylor cone and droplet formation

Electrospray Process

2) Droplet fission

Electrospray Process

2) Droplet fission and the Rayleigh limit

Rayleigh Equation:

$$z_R e = 8\pi(\epsilon_0 \gamma R^3)^{1/2}$$

z_R = number of excess charges
in the droplet

R = droplet radius

γ = solvent surface tension

≈ 20 offspring droplets
take away $\approx 15\%$ of the charges
and $\approx 2\%$ of the mass
of the parent droplet

Electrospray Process

3) Ion production from the droplets

Ion evaporation

Charged residue

Chain ejection

Electrospray of phospholipids

Electrospray of sugars

Electrospray of peptides and proteins

Side chain protonation

Arginine

Lysine

Histidine

Side chain deprotonation

Glutamic acid

Aspartic acid

ESI-MS spectrum of a peptide in positive ion mode

M = 1500 Da

Electrospray of proteins in positive ion mode

Charge state distributions: How to determine M and z ?

What analyte properties influence the level of charging (average z)?

Cytochrome c

4 % acetic acid
pH = 2.6

0 % acetic acid
pH = 5.2

Globular large analytes → charged residue (top) Denatured chains → chain ejection (bottom)

Small ion
→ ion
evaporation

Several mechanisms can compete

Intrinsically disordered proteins show broad, often multimodal, charge state distributions

Proteins with both compact and disordered regions: Bead Ejection Mechanism (BEM)

Bead Ejection Mechanism (BEM): a hybrid (and intermediate) ionization mechanism

Response factors (What determines the intensities in ESI?)

$$I_{\text{mes,A}} = P \cdot f \cdot [A]_{\text{surf}}$$

P = efficiency of transfer in the mass spectrometer

f = efficiency of ending up in offspring droplet

$$I_{\text{mes,A}} = P \cdot f \cdot \frac{K_A [A]}{K_A [A] + K_E [E]} \cdot [Q]$$

Competition from other analytes or electrolytes

[Q] = concentration of excess charges at the surface (mol/L) = $[A]_{\text{surf}} + [E]_{\text{surf}}$

[Q] = $I/F\Gamma$ I = current (Cb/s)

F = Faraday constant (Cb/mol)

Γ = flow rate (L/s)

Spatial discrimination in ion response

Nano-Electrospray Ionisation (nano-ESI)

More than just nanoflow electrospray?

[Wilm & Mann, Anal. Chem. \(1996\) 68, 1](#)

→ Flow rates of nanoliters/min

Figure 2. Electrospray spectrum of a 10^{-6} M peptide solution in an aqueous 10^{-1} M NaCl solution. The solution was electrosprayed without any nebulizer or sheath flow assistance. The spectrum is dominated by the salt clusters, but the peptide is still discernible.

Sub- μm nanospray tips for native protein MS (less adducts upon charged residue process)

